

PYTHON DASTURLASH TILI

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu tezida Python daturining yaratilish tarixi va ushbu dasturlash tilining imkoniyatlari haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'z: python, operatsion tizim, dasturiy kod.

Python - yuqori bosqichli dasturlash tili hisoblanib, tirli xil ilovalarni yaratish uchun mo'ljallangan. Ya'ni Python dasturlash tili yordamida veb-ilovalar, o'yin ilovalari, oddiy (nastol'niy) dasturlar yaratish hamda berilganlar bazasi bilan ishlash mumkin. Ayniqsa Python dasturlash tilining tezlik bilan tarqalishiga uning mashinali o'rgatish va sun'iy intellekt sohalaridagi tadqiqot ishlarida keng qo'llanilishi sabab bo'lgan.

Python dasturlash tiliga 1991 yil Golland dasturchisi Guido van Rossum asos solgan. Shundan beri ushbu til rivojlanishning ulkan yo'lini bosib o'tdi va 2000yilda 2.0 versiyasi, 2008 yil esa 3.0 versiyalari chiqarildi. Versiyalar orasidagimuddatning uzoqligiga qaramasdan doima versiya ostilari chiqariladi. Shundayqilib, ushbu material eng oxirgi 3.7 versiyasi asosida tuzilgan.

Python dasturlash tilining asosiy xususiyatlari quyidagilardan iborat:

Skriptli til. Dastur kodi skriptlar ko'rinishida bo'ladi;

Turli dasturlash paradigmlarni, xususan ob'ektga yo'naltirilgan va funksional paradigmlarni o'zida mujassamlagan;

Skriptlar bilan ishlash uchun interpretator kerak bo'lib, u skriptni ishga tushiradi va bajaradi.

Portativlik va platformaga bog'liqmaslik. Kop'yuterda qanday operasion tizim Windows, Mac OS, Linux bo'lishidan qat'iy nazar, ushbu operasion tizimda interpretator mavjud bo'lsa, foydalanuvchi tomonidan yozilgan skript kod bajariladi.

Xotiraning avtomatik boshqarilishi; Turlarga dinamik ajratilishi;

Pythonda dasturning bajarilishi quyidagicha bo'ladi: Dastlab mant muharririda ushbu dasturlash tili asosida ifodalar ketma-ketligidan iborat skript kod yoziladi. Ushbu yozilgan skript kod barajirilish uchun interpretatorga uzatiladi. Interpretator skript kodni oraliq baytkodga tarjima qiladi. Keyin virtual mashina

baytkodni operatsion tizimda bajariladigan instruksiyalar (mashina buyruqlari) to'plamiga o'tkazadi.

Rasm №1. Pythonda dasturning bajarilishi jarayoni.

Shu ta'kidlash lozimki, rasman interpretator tomonidan dastlabki kodning baytkodga tarjima qilinishi va virtual mashinaning ushbu baytkodni mashina buyruqlari to'plamiga o'tkazilishi ikkita turli jarayon bo'lsada, ammo amalda ular bitta interpretatorning o'zida birlashtirilgan.

Python juda oddiy dasturlash tili bo'lib, u ixcham shu bilan bir vaqtda sodda va tushinarli sintaksisga ega. Shu sababli Python o'rganish uchun juda oson til sifatida butun dunyoda eng tez tarqalayotgan tillardan biri sifatida e'tirof etiladi. Bundan tashqari ushbu tilda hozirgi kunga kelib, turli sohalarga (veb, o'yin, mul'timediya, ilmiy tadqiqot) mo'ljallangan katta hajmdagi kutbxonalar majmui yaratilgan bo'lib, uning tobora mashhurlashib borishiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

Pythonni o'rnatish. Pythonda dastur tuzish uchun interpretator kerak bo'ladi. Uni kompyuteringizdagi o'rnatilgan operatsion tizim turiga mos ravishda <https://www.python.org> rasmiy saytidan kerakli versiyasini tushirib olishingiz mumkin.

Foydalanilgan saytlar ro'yxati:

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